

MUSIC PAINTED EMOTIONAL RENAISSANCE PICTURES

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Annotation. The Renaissance is considered as the development of Western Europe, Middle Asia, China and Iran. Competition between neighboring states encouraged cultural innovation, which in the Renaissance led to a revival of ancient culture, realistic literature, and interconnected artistic expressions through sound, words, color, and gesture. This article discusses how people’s feelings and emotions were expressed through music and painting during the Renaissance in Western Europe. Renaissance art focused on reviving ancient culture, realism, and human emotion, while medieval art emphasized the spiritual world. In addition, music genres have evolved and changed from simple (sacred) – non-lyrical, into complex (secular) –lyrical music genres. As culture developed, humanity began to think more deeply about itself and its emotions. They tried to depict emotions, national culture and ordinary life through music, poetry and paintings. In particular, the direct connection between music and paintings enriched realism and humanity. At the same time, there were also disagreements between religiosity and humanity. Nevertheless, the main point was humanism. Artists put forward the idea of humanism, and as a result, the depiction of spiritual and emotional experiences was absorbed into music and paintings.

Аннотация. Ренессанс считается периодом развития Западной Европы, Центральной Азии, Китая и Ирана. Соперничество между соседними государствами способствовало культурным инновациям, что в эпоху Возрождения привело к возрождению античной культуры, реалистической литературы и взаимосвязанных художественных выражений через звук, слово, цвет и жест. В данной статье рассматривается, как чувства и эмоции людей выражались через музыку и живопись в эпоху Ренессанса в Западной Европе. Искусство Ренессанса было сосредоточено на возрождении античной культуры, реализме и человеческих эмоциях, тогда как средневековое искусство акцентировало духовный мир.

Кроме того, музыкальные жанры эволюционировали и изменялись от простых (сакральных) — нелирических форм к сложным (светским) — лирическим музыкальным жанрам. По мере развития культуры человечество начало глубже осмысливать себя и свои эмоции. Люди стремились передать чувства, национальную культуру и повседневную жизнь через музыку, поэзию и живопись. Особенно тесная связь между музыкой и живописью обогатила реализм и гуманизм. В то же время существовали и противоречия между религиозностью и гуманизмом. Тем не менее, основной идеей оставался гуманизм. Художники выдвигали идею гуманизма, и в результате изображение духовных и эмоциональных переживаний нашло отражение в музыке и живописи.

Keywords: art, mood, connected techniques, painters, painting, musical principles

Ключевые слова: искусство, настроение, взаимосвязанные техники, художники, живопись, музыкальные принципы.

Introduction. Although in the 14th-16th century, innovation of culture was widely spread around the world, the special shift in cultural renewal, or the term "Renaissance," only reached Western Europe. During the Renaissance, in Europe the interaction of secular and religious learning fulfilled each other and made a growing emphasis under the term "humanism." (Yu, 2016) As a consequence, throughout this term, attention to realism and human life has increased compared to religious beliefs. As various fields of art developed during the Renaissance and the Middle Ages, some parts of each artwork expressed human emotions and feelings, which means artists' practices evolved and were directed to humanism. As Simion explained, "The language of art hits different, but there are also common features that confine arts." (2021) It means that all artworks contain similarities in some cases, which helps us to understand the same meaning in different frames, whether it is composition or painting, literature art, or a form of stage art. Painters did not limit themselves to painting, nor did musicians restrict their creativity to composing music. What unified their work was precisely this outlook. They added elements from related fields to their own craft and created beyond the boundaries of a single discipline.

Renaissance artists and musicians used new techniques to express human feelings more deeply, making visual art feel “musical” and music feel “pictorial”. For instance, painters’ musical principles referred to the way visual artists applied rhythm, harmony, balance, and emotional resonance – concepts drawn from music – to structure and enrich their compositions.

Mood Expressed Through Art. Influence of art and music to human emotions was one of the main points during the Middle Ages. Renaissance is not said as a revival period in vain. In this time, people knew and learnt only about God, and then thought about themselves. After several stages of reviving, people learned to put themselves at the first place, more precisely, artists from that time push up this theory to everybody through their arts. They painted, composed, built - everything was related to human emotions which artists wanted to display at first. According to Chant, initially, the main point was on religion (1), however, after renaissance, both religiosity and humanism became equal to each other (2001). As Yu said in 2016, musical and artistically world in the Renaissance, shifted human emotions and experiences to the pinpoint of life. And this demonstrates that creativity of artists rose as well as realism. For instance, types of music became realistic and complicated. Compositions which were played with multiple instruments, and dance music started to be popular in 14th-15th centuries. As an example, we can take German composer Michael Praetorius’ musical collection named *Terpsichore*. This was one of the most popular complicated dance music collection in 16th. This compilation indicated real life, sadness and happiness, emotions and feelings of people. They just felt it while listening to this music. Initially, music used to be played as a background voice in church, whereas in 16th, this concept was changed and expanded, and people built trust that music can be used to show emotions. As a consequence, striving to humanism enhanced, people shared their intends by composing, painting and creating - all of them was real-experiences of human life.

Overall, change of human worldview affected by this golden era (Levy, 2001). The core formation of European culture was humanism and changes during this period of time. Prioritizing humanity over religion modified opinions and beliefs.

1. Two people in the room

Connected Techniques in Music and Painting. Rhythmic composition and color in paintings keep balance with blending in music, which makes them depended to each other. As it determined in the first paragraph, composing music was improved, various musical instruments played the same notes, differences were harmonized. However, harmonization of music and human voice took some steps, to become perfect. Hard music expressed sorrow, while light music represented felicity. Exactly so paintings described real life, characteristics and mood. But at the same time, the question may arise whether similarities and contradictions have arisen between them. At the first glance, it is unrecognizable. However, as Fleming said, overall art is unique idea where people can share their conceptions and beliefs, communicate artists' ideas perspectives (1983). Therefore, both art styles perform the same task. Principally, since ancient times pictures shared some kind of meaning, as exactly during the renaissance main goal wasn't changed. After all, painters started to combine musical changes to their artworks. This approach is called "compositional handling". According to Simion, "Each of the artists took a personal ', different approach in style, color, compositional treatment, social and artistic messages." (2021) This commence was about writing instruments on paintings. By this, artists made historical change,

they highlighted modification during the renaissance, leading to realism and humanism. Musical instruments became complicated, older one changed with new one. For instance, in 17th century instrument called vihuela, equivalent of lute, changed with guitar (Simion, 2021). Thus, music harmonies switched to paintings, painting new instruments was also rhythm between them. Evaluation of colors and palettes in the paintings happened, during the harmonisation of art. Vecellio Tiziano, Italian painter, teacher of Vecellio school was the greatest painter in the renaissance. In 2021, Simion claimed that, he was very professional on his work, each color and tone was used by him directly approached. His era was divided into golden period, and silver period by critics. Artworks of Tiziano are the greatest example for harmony and blending between paintings.

Painters' Musical Principles. During the Renaissance, painters were not only involved in paintings, but also in composing. This clearly shows the connection between two art forms. The main example for great artists during the renaissance could be Leonardo da Vinci. He was not just artist, he was musician, inventor, scientist. His originality was about how he thought about art as a unique idea. One of the most famous artwork of

Da Vinci's "The Last Supper" (2). This painting about the dinner with Jesus around his disciples. Jesus was in the middle, surrounded by other people, which makes the sense of musical rhythm. According to Farago (1992) and Vasari (1568), "Leonardo's view that "painting is a superior art to music" underscores the impact of visual art on human perception, while music's emotional influence was regarded as addressing the soul on a more profound level." Thus, Da Vinci could play an instrument called lira da braccio, and he improvised several compositions while playing with this instrument. His perspective about music and art was distinctive: music can stimulate emotions, while paintings keep them frozen. However, according to Tokgoz, "Both artworks aim to provide the viewer and listener with a profound spiritual experience."(2025) Leonardo's paints remind rhythm, balance and melody - musical parts, while compositions highlights pause, dynamic and "light notes". Nevertheless, all art spheres main direction was about humanism, reality and human-experience of people (Mahoney, 2023). Art forms build strong relationship between nature and human, which was widely spread during the Renaissance.

2.The Last Supper

Conclusion. To conclude, after evolution of Europe, complete update of art and humanity changed peoples' perspectives, and it was true historical event. Art forms fulfilled each other, painters and musicians shared techniques and emotional designs. Each artwork made a sense of human importance in their lives, combining musical experiences into painting or by combining stage art into musical performance. Thus, music, art made another level of life, creativity and reality during the Renaissance.

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